

Related works

SecVisor creates a tiny hypervisor as TCB at higher privilege than host OS to protect the integrity of its kernel. In contrast, SecFortress creates mediator at the same privilege as host OS, introducing fewer context switches and less overhead. Furthermore, SecFortress aims to ensure the isolation among different guest VMs, while Secvisor focuses on kernel integrity protection within guest VMs, which can be used together with SecFortress to build a comprehensive protection for cloud platforms.

SeL4 is a formally verified microkernel, not including common OS components. Such components need to be implemented separately as user programs, increasing development burden. HyperWall implements memory isolation using CIP tables and requires support from hardware, e.g., FPGA. In contrast, SecFortress can be deployed on commercial X86 platforms. Moreover, HyperWall requires modification to guest OS, while SecFortress does not.

Additional security analysis.

1. Against the mediator

- (1) **Tampering with SecFortress Code.** During the system boot phase, we use secure boot to ensure the integrity of the mediator. After booting, the mediator measures the integrity of the system's code and sets all code to be write-protected. In addition, the mediator prohibits mapping new executable memory to outerOS or HypBox, so it can defend code injection attacks.
- (2) **Bypass the mediator protection.** The protection mechanism could be bypassed if the sensitive instructions in Table II get executed directly by non-TCB components. SecFortress dynamically checks and unmaps those instructions in non-TCB components. For new instruction injection attack, SecFortress defends against it by write-protection. Regarding ROP-based attacks, SecFortress checks the result before a bad consequence occurs. In addition, a binary scanner is used to ensure that there are no such instructions (reuse of ROP gadget) in unexpected code regions. Hence, there is no way to bypass the mediator protection.
- (3) **DMA attack.** An attacker may try to access sensitive memory regions by leveraging DMA. SecFortress defends against such attacks by controlling IOMMU, which is used for DMA I/O address translation. The mediator controls the mapping updates and information in IOMMU, and strictly constrains the scope that each guest VM can access.

2. Against other components

- (1) **Breach of confidentiality.** Normally, a host OS can access any physical page or modify the memory layouts. SecFortress unmaps HypBox-related memory regions in the kernel master-page-table to prevent host OS from accessing the HypBoxes' memory. Furthermore, a compromised host OS may attempt to remap the physical memory of hypervisor to its address space, or other processes. Since physical memory is loaded into the CPU cache in a plain-text state and is not isolated in cacheline, it may leak sensitive information once the host OS launches the above attack. Such an attack can be defeated

by SecFortress. SecFortress sets the kernel master page-table-pages to be write-protected, and forces the attribute certification prior to memory mapping updates. For the page tables of other processes, since all processes' page tables depend on the kernel master-page-table to add new mappings, SecFortress can limit them as long as it controls the master-page-table. Similarly, a compromised HypBox also cannot access sensitive information of others because it has no permission to modify its memory view.

- (2) **Integrity violation.** A compromised host OS may try to violate the integrity of the HypBox by directly tampering with the memory. SecFortress defends against such an attack by controlling memory mapping updates and memory access permissions. This means that a compromised host OS does not have permission to modify the physical pages that have been assigned to HypBoxes. Moreover, during HypBox creation, a compromised host OS may try to write malicious code or data to a specific physical page, which will be assigned to the HypBox. SecFortress protects this attack by zeroising the physical pages before assignment.